

Dividing by Zero: An Out-of-the-Box Approach.

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Introduction

Standard Algebra has yet to adduce enough evidence to extensively demystify the claims of dividing by zero; Whiles in practice ‘Infinity’ (∞) is the acceptable or rather unavoidable answer when a non-zero number is divided by zero, on the other hand, the idea of ‘Infinity’ has very few practical applications in the daily human experience. Hence, this research makes use of an innovative approach to Dividing by Zero, which approach still, is not in any way foreign to Standard Algebra.

And so the purpose of this paper is to offer a complementary concept on dividing by zero and to enrich already existing knowledge and discussions in research, academic, industrial and other forums bordering around the relevance and applications of dividing by zero.

An Out-of-the-Box Approach

Considering the following sequence S_d :

$$S_d = \frac{1}{n}, \frac{1}{n-1}, \dots, \frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{9}, \frac{1}{8}, \frac{1}{7}, \frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{1}, \frac{1}{0}.$$

It may be seen that the sequence S_d may be considered as a ‘special’ Geometric Sequence that progresses by a ‘dynamic’ ratio r_n given as:

$$r_d = \left(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{(n-1)} \right) \text{ or } r_d = \frac{1}{n^2-n}$$

Unlike a usual Geometric Sequence with just a simple common ratio, this ‘special’ Geometric Sequence, S_d comes with ‘dynamic’ ratios r_d which may be seen to automatically form another sequence, S_n .

And so this second sequence S_n is represented as:

$$S_n = \frac{1}{n^2-n}, \dots, \frac{1}{90}, \frac{1}{72}, \frac{1}{56}, \frac{1}{42}, \frac{1}{30}, \frac{1}{20}, \frac{1}{12}, \frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{0},$$

And out of this second sequence, S_n a new series, U_r

$$U_r = \frac{1}{n^2-n} \dots + \frac{1}{90} + \frac{1}{72} + \frac{1}{56} + \frac{1}{42} + \frac{1}{30} + \frac{1}{20} + \frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{0},$$

To serve the purposes of Summing up (from Zero) to Infinity, U_r may be re-arranged into U_n as follows:

$$U_n = \frac{1}{0} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{20} + \frac{1}{30} + \frac{1}{42} + \frac{1}{56} + \frac{1}{72} + \frac{1}{90} \dots + \frac{1}{n^2+n}$$

The *Out-of-the-Box Approach* is about identifying the patterns in the series, U_n generated from the Sequence, S_d and systematically taking cues from these patterns to solving or resolving the term, $\frac{1}{0}$ in U_n .

Partial Summation

The term, $\frac{1}{0}$ in U_n can be evaluated by the *Partial Summation* of U_n at $n = 0$: is:

$$\sum_{n=0}^0 \frac{\{(n) + (n + 1)\} (n)}{\{(n + 1)\} (n)}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^0 \frac{(2n + 1)}{(n + 1)} = \frac{1}{1} = 1$$

Sum to Infinity

Then expression for the *Sum to Infinity* of the series U_n is also found by:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\{(n) + (n + 1)\} (n)}{\{(n + 1)\} (n)}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2n + 1)}{(n + 1)} = 2$$

Then the term, $\frac{1}{0}$ in U_n can be evaluated by *Partial Summation* of U_n when $n = 0$: is:

$$\sum_{n=0}^0 \frac{(2n + 1)}{(n + 1)} = \frac{1}{1} = 1$$

Results and Discussion

Therefore $\frac{1}{0} = \frac{1}{1} = \mathbf{1}$

Then generally $\frac{N}{0} = \frac{1}{0} \times N = \frac{1}{1} \times N = N$ where N could be any non-zero number.

So that for example, $\frac{145}{0} = \frac{1}{0} \times 145 = \frac{1}{1} \times 145 = \mathbf{145}$

So dividing any number by Zero (0) gives the same answer as dividing that same number by One (1) and which is that same number itself. The answer obtained in this approach is easier to understand and to relate to in contrast to the “infinity” of standard practice.

Conclusion

There are many situations in real life where the complexity or perplexity of dividing by zero often occurs, and with time this realization in regard to the solution provided in this paper will be more acceptable and appreciated.